

Kinetics of Bromine Addition to Chalkones

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The bimolecular rate constant (k) and activation energy (E) for the bromination of various mono-, di- and tri-substituted chalkones in methanol, nitrobenzene and benzene have been measured. Changes in rate with substitution are mainly due to changes in E . The frequency factor and the solvent effects on rate have been studied. From the slope of the regression line fitted to $\log k$ and σ_0 data, the ' ρ ' value has been calculated. A probable mechanism has been suggested.

It appears from a study of the literature that the addition reaction of bromine to chalkones has not been systematically examined with regard to mechanism, kinetics and the factors influencing the rate. The kinetics of bromination of olefinic compounds was first studied by Herz and Mylius¹. Roberts and Kimball² have studied the kinetics of bromination of olefins and have provided evidence to show that the electrophilic attack by the halogen molecule is the rate determining stage of these additions. Mortan and Robertson³, Hartman and Robertson⁴ have studied the kinetics of halogen addition to α , β -unsaturated acids and nitro cinnamic acid. Further Robertson *et al.*⁵ have studied the kinetics of halogen addition to α , β -unsaturated ketones and quinones.

In the present work, the kinetics of bromination of a large number of mono, di- and trisubstituted derivatives of chalkones in benzene, nitrobenzene and methanol have been studied. The Arrhenius parameters have been discussed. The applicability of the Hammett equation⁶ has been discussed. From the slope of the regression line fitted to $\log k$ and σ_0 data⁷ for the m -substituted compounds, the value of ' ρ ', the reaction constant, was calculated at various temperatures. The effective σ values ($\bar{\sigma}$) and resonance interaction energy ($\Delta\Delta F_p$) for the various substituents have been determined. These values provide useful information about the electron distribution in the transition state. A mechanism involving the formation of an intermediate bromonium ion on the lines of accepted mechanism for addition reaction of halogens to olefins has been suggested.

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2. I. Roberts and G. E. Kimball, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, **57**, 947.
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6. (a) L. P. Hammett. 'Physical Organic Chemistry', McGraw Hill Book, New York, 1940, pp. 76.
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EXPERIMENTAL

The chalcones were prepared and purified according to known methods.⁸

The solvents used were in 'AnalaR' quality.

The method of rate measurement was similar to that of Rout *et al.*⁹, by estimating the excess of bromine with standard thiosulphate left at different intervals of time. The rate constant together with the energy of activation are given in Table I.

DISCUSSION

A two step mechanism for the reaction of chalcones with bromine, as indicated below is suggested.

The first step of the process is shown to involve the electrophilic addition of a positive bromine atom to the double bond in chalcone molecule resulting in the formation of a bromonium ion. Due to the presence of the carbonyl group, the double bond in the chalcone molecule is polarised towards the carbonyl group. This causes the positive bromine atom to add-up at the carbon atom adjacent to the carbonyl group as this carbon atom is supposed to possess a fractional negative charge. In the second step the dibromo chalcone is formed by the trans opening of the bromonium ion by the negative bromide ion.

The first step of the reaction is slow and is, therefore, the rate determining step. The reaction obeys the second order kinetics. The course of the reaction has been followed by estimating the bromine left at different intervals of time.

On the basis of the above mechanism electron repelling substituents in R and R' will enhance the reaction rate and the electron attracting substituents will retard the rate.

The results given in Table I indicate that the reaction is facilitated by groups such as methyl and methoxy in both benzoyl and phenyl groups of the chalcone molecule and retarded by groups such as nitro, chloro, bromo etc. The effect of the substituents in the benzoyl group of the chalcone molecule is not large. On the other hand, the influence of substituents in the phenyl group of the chalcone molecule is appreciably pronounced, the methyl group increasing and the nitro group reducing the rate. With the methyl group at 4-position, the rate was so rapid that it could not be measured in nitrobenzene and methanol. The value

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of specific reaction rate, at 30° and the energy of activation in nitrobenzene are listed in Table I.

TABLE I

Values of specific reaction rate and energy of activation : $k \times 10^3$ litre mole⁻¹ sec.⁻¹.

Name of the chalkone	H	3-NO ₂	4-NO ₂	2-NO ₂	2-Cl
$k_{30} \times 10^3$ litre/mole ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹	39.81	9.674	2.533	0.5971	3.58
E in K.Cal/mole	17.13	20.26	28.87	34.35	22.10
Name of the chalkone	4-Cl	2,4-Cl	2,4-Cl 5-NO ₂	3-NO ₂ , 4-Cl	2-Cl 5-NO ₂
$k_{30} \times 10^3$ litre/mole ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹	42.40	4.51	3.548	25.31	27.32
E in K.Cal/mole	17.50	21.64	24.87	21.18	24.41
Name of the chalkone	3'-NO ₂	3'-Br	4'-Br	4'-Cl	4'-Cl 3'-NO ₂
$k_{30} \times 10^3$ litre/mole ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹	26.43	26.42	36.39	56.80	15.67
E in K.Cal/mole	18.88	18.88	17.50	11.05	12.43
Name of the substituent	3'-NO ₂ , 4'-Br	4'-CH ₃			
$k_{30} \times 10^3$ litre mole ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹	15.22	71.15			
E in K.Cal/mole	19.34	8.987			

Frequency Factor : The values of $\log k_{35}$ of chalkone derivatives have been plotted against the activation energy, the plot being a straight line with theoretical slope of $-2.303RT$.

TABLE II

The energy of activation and the frequency factor at 35° for the reaction of bromine with chalkone and its derivatives.

Sl. no.	Name of the substituent in chalkone	$k_{35} \times 10^3$ litre mole ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹	E K.Cal/mole	$\log A$
1.	H	55.8	17.1392	10.826
2.	2'-nitro-	48.93	18.885	11.98
3.	3'-bromo-	48.05	18.885	11.94
4.	4-chloro-	76.05	17.5028	11.255
5.	4'-bromo-	75.98	17.5028	11.2107
6.	3'-Nitro 4'-bromo-	21.83	18.345	11.96
7.	2,4-Dichloro-	7.627	21.648	10.88
8.	3-Nitro-	16.93	20.266	12.00
9.	3-Nitro 4-chloro-	54.83	21.1876	13.81
10.	2-chloro-	6.86	20.1058	13.37
11.	2,4-Dichloro 5-nitro-	6.38	24.87	14.30

The value of Z (Collision number) decreases with increase in molecular weight of the reactants. Since bromine is one of the common reactant throughout the series of reactions studied in nitrobenzene and the molecular weight of chalkone varies slightly from one compound to another, a constant value of Z is obtained and consequently $\log A$ is constant for the reaction series. But for the points which do not lie on the line, the following explanation is given. Molecules of the reactant may be surrounded by solvent molecules due to solvation and this gives rise to increase in molecular weight of the solvated compound. So the number of effective collision Z between reactant molecules will decrease and thus the value of PZ decreases. But in those cases where higher value of PZ are observed, solvation less than the normal ones (those which give rise to points on the straight line) is indicated and this leads to higher value of Z .

Solvent effect : The change in the specific rate constants for the reaction of bromine with chalkones in different solvents follows the order :

Methyl alcohol > nitro benzene > benzene.

TABLE III

The energy of activation and the frequency factors at 30° for the addition reaction of bromine with chalkone in different solvents.

Sl. no.	Name of the chalkone	Solvent	$k_{30} \times 10^3$ lit./mole/sec	E . in K. Cal/mole	$\log PZ$	$\Delta S^\ddagger$
1.	Chalkone	C_6H_6	19.05	17.842	11.08	-17.48
	Chalkone	$C_6H_5NO_2$	39.81	17.139	10.64	-19.50
	Chalkone	CH_3OH	127.00	8.75	5.375	-40.80
2.	4-Chloro chalkone	C_6H_6	20.74	19.345	12.194	- 7.15
	4-Chloro chalkone	$C_6H_5NO_2$	42.40	17.50	11.167	-14.12
	4-Chloro chalkone	CH_3OH	148.90	7.369	4.54	-45.48

In the bromination of chalkones the product and hence probably the activated complex are more polar than the reactants. Solvation by the highly polar solvents, methanol and nitrobenzene will, therefore, lower the activation energy from its value in a less polar solvent such as benzene.

In benzene the frequency factor is high in comparison to the frequency factor in other solvents. As benzene is a non-polar solvent, there will be less possibility of solvation and hence the complexity of the activated complex will also be less. A higher value of ' ρ ' is, therefore, observed. The energy of activation is also high in benzene because the release of heat of solvation by the activated complex is low.

It is evident from Table III that the entropy of activation is negative and changes with the solvent, becoming more as the polarity of the solvent decreases. It follows from this that the rates of reaction increase with polarity of the solvent and that the increase may be governed by the change in entropy of activation.

Hammett Equation : A regression line was fitted to the $\log k$ data against σ_0 data for the *m*-substituted and unsubstituted compounds at each temperature. The reaction constant (ρ), correlation coefficient (r) and intercept with the ordinate ($\log k_0$) are listed in Table IV.

TABLE IV

The values of ρ , r and $\log k_0$ from the plot of $\log k$ and σ_0 data for the addition of bromine to chalkones

Temperature in °C	' ρ '	r	$\log k_0$
25	-0.40	0.9832	1.35
30	-0.36	0.9765	1.56
40	-0.32	0.9836	1.81

The values of ' ρ ' appears to vary inversely as the temperature, decreasing with rise of temperature. In agreement with this conclusion, the Arrhenius parameters indicate that the reaction series is isoentropic.¹⁰ As is expected, the negative value of ' ρ ' indicates that the reaction is retarded by electron withdrawal from the reaction site.

Considering several reaction series and numerous data it has been suggested by Van Bekkum *et al.*¹¹, that in those cases where a substituent enters into mesomeric para interaction with the reaction centre, a multiplicity of (exalted) σ values is observed. This holds for $+M$ as well as for $-M$ substituents. But in the absence of mesomeric para interaction, σ values are reasonably constant. The effective σ values ($\bar{\sigma}$) were calculated from the expression.

$$\bar{\sigma} = \frac{\log k - \log k_0}{\rho}$$

As the effective σ values ($\bar{\sigma}$) in general are not suitable criteria for judging mesomeric para interactions, free energy ($\Delta\Delta F_p$)¹¹ difference terms have also been calculated for evaluation of mesomeric para interactions.

$$\Delta\Delta F_p = -2.303RT' \rho (\bar{\sigma} - \sigma_0)$$

This expression involves not only the exaltation of σ but ρ and T' as well. The effective σ values ($\bar{\sigma}$) and the corresponding resonance energy differences ($\Delta\Delta F_p$) are given in Table V.

The magnitude of the resonance interaction in the transition state is quite small by comparison with, for example, the solvolysis of α , α -4-methyl benzyl chloride¹² but it must be emphasised that the influence of resonance interaction in the transition state is to be judged

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11. H. Van Bekkum, P. E. Verkade and B. M. Wepster, *Rec. Trav. Chim.*, 1959, **78**, 815.

12. H. C. Brown, J. D. Brady, M. Grayson and W. H. Bonner, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, **79**, 1897.

by the magnitude of such interaction compared with that of the polar contribution to the relative free energy of activation *i.e.*, by the ratio :

$$\Delta\Delta F_p/2\cdot303RT\sigma_0 = (\bar{\sigma}-\sigma_0)/\sigma_0$$

The effective σ values for the reaction series differ from σ_0 in case of the 4'-methyl group and 4'-nitro group.

TABLE V

Effective σ values and resonance interaction energy for para substituted compounds at 40°.

Substituent on Chalkone	4'-CH ₃	4'-Cl	4'-Br	4'-NO ₂
$\bar{\sigma}$	-0.81	-0.12	+0.10	+0.093
σ_0	-0.15	+0.27	+0.26	+0.82
$\bar{\sigma}-\sigma_0$	-0.66	-0.39	-0.16	-0.727
$\Delta\Delta F_p$ K.Cal/mole	-0.3047	-0.1800	-0.0737	-0.3357

The effective σ values ($\bar{\sigma}$) and the magnitude of the resonance interaction energy for the 4'-methyl group and 4'-nitro group reveals that there is important and substantial resonance interaction between the substituent and reaction centre in the transition state. This is in accord with a transition state which may be represented as follows :

The above picture of the transition state is consistent with the negative sign of the ($\Delta\Delta F_p$) values for both 4'-methyl and 4'-nitro groups which indicates that there is greater resonance in the transition state than in the reactant state¹¹. On the basis of the above transition state, the retarding effect of the nitro group can be easily understood since the nitro group withdraws π electron density from $-\text{CH}=\text{CH}-$ group to which the bromine molecule adds up. The rate accelerating effect of the methyl group can be similarly accounted for, since it increases the electron density of the $-\text{CH}=\text{CH}-$ by virtue of its electron donating nature.

Mechanism of the Reaction : The following mechanism which is in conformity with that proposed for addition of bromine to olefins is suggested.

The first step of the process is the electrophilic attack by the halogen which becomes at least partly polarised in the sense $\text{Br}^{\delta+} \cdot \text{Br}^{\delta-}$, on the carbon atom adjacent to the carbonyl group of the chalkone molecule. Thus by the direct action of bromine on the ethylenic linkage of chalkone, formation of an intermediate of the type II called the bromonium ion

is suggested. The electrophilic attack of the bromine molecule is the rate determining stage of these reactions. In the second stage which is considerably faster than the first stage, the cyclic intermediate bromonium ion is opened up by direct SN_2 process initiated by the anion.

When the reaction is carried out in a polar solvent like methanol, methoxy bromo chalkone is formed. This provides conclusive evidence in favour of the mechanism suggested.

It was at first considered that the formation of methoxy bromo chalkone may be due to reaction of methanol with bromine as shown below :

From the equation it appears that if the concentration of methyl hypobromite controls the reaction rate, then an increased concentration of bromide ion would have retarding effect on the reaction by shifting the equilibrium towards the left. This is actually observed. Since the hydrogen ion and bromide ion enter equally into this equilibrium, an increased concentration of hydrogen ion should likewise diminish the rate of the reaction. But it was found that the rate does not appreciably diminish by the hydrogen ions. These results are, therefore, incompatible with the idea that the concentration of methyl hypobromite controls the rate of this reaction and also with the idea that methyl hypobromite is responsible for the formation of chalkone methoxy bromide.

A second mechanism is also possible on the lines suggested by Ogg¹³ for the bromination of stilbene.

This mechanism postulates a negatively charged intermediate for the formation of dibromides.

13. J. Ogg, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 57, 2727.

In this case we might have for the methoxy bromide the negative intermediate here competing with the chalcone-bromide ion intermediate for reaction with bromine. If this mechanism is correct, then the added acid should powerfully diminish the rate by decreasing the concentration of the respective form which is not observed. Therefore, this mechanism can not explain the observed facts.

The mechanism suggested by us and indicated earlier is capable of explaining the formation of both the dibromide and methoxy bromide.

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